

A Language of Absence: Inhabiting What is More than Potential

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In exploring domains that extend beyond conventional reach, current language is often inadequate. Potential could be described as dynamic happening in suspension, a state of latent holding of possible measure, whatever the framework. In terms of critical framework, absence is non-space wherein even potential is in abeyance. Why would the elaboration of such 'absence-potential' be relevant or important? Because, it might lend itself to the creation of the possibility of measure. And in occupying realms prior to measure, there is the figure of what might be manifest reality. Mathematics might be viewed as the beginning of the measure of any such manifest reality, however being within the sphere of expression it is likely inadequate in approximating what is prior to any possible measure.

In attempting to describe something like 'absence-potential', it might make some sense to bring in possible descriptors such as 'translational space' which might capture the state of potential for space in language that might be shared during imaginative discourse. In extending language to fit the creation of a logic that is yet to be explored, there arises the risk of comparison against established or probable sense making. One might ask whether language could ever delineate what lies before the potential for manifest reality. In some way, the term absence is apt in elucidating formlessness or statelessness. 'Stateless' does not accurately convey the abiding prior to any form of measure while the term absence or perhaps absence-potential might.

In a strange way, absence cannot be a space, it can actually only be its own potential, hence the emphasis on what this author introduces as absence-potential. In conceiving this, it becomes feasible to approximate abiding prior to the measure of space. That is perhaps the most important implication of bringing into expression such unusual terminology. In conceiving what might be prior to the possibility of space, one would need to appeal to common reason. Even if we restrict ourselves to neologisms such as just 'absence-potential' and 'translational space', we begin to extend beyond measure, and just that is an exercise worth attempting!

The potential of measure, begins to bring into focus the contemplation of absolute preconditions and that is the whole purpose of this brief discussion. Where abiding in the realm of measure is restrictive, inhabiting more than what is potential can be very freeing but to make that credible, this kind of language becomes important.

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